

SO2 Instrument Description

Last updated 1 Dec 2022

SO2 measurements are made by the FAAM Airborne Laboratory using a pulsed UV fluorescence spectrometer, specifically a Thermo Fisher Scientific model TEi-43i TLE SO2 analyser. This instrument has been flown since 2016, and customized as described in the flow diagram below.

An external PermaPure Multi-strand Nafion dryer (part no. PD-50T-24MPR) lowers the moisture content from the air being sampled and therefore minimises fluorescence quenching by water vapour. The dryer is plumbed using a reflux setup, which returns the dry sample back to the dryer sheath for use as the purge gas after it has gone through the detector. Since this method uses all of the dry sample as the purge gas, only the sample flow required for analysis passes through the dryer which results in high drying efficiency. The vacuum on the purge gas is provided by the analyser's internal vacuum pump.

The instrument sample flow rate was increased from approximately 0.5 to 2.0 SLPM, to reduce lag times and speed up instrumental response times. A mass flow controller (MFC3, Alicat Scientific, part no. MCS-5SLPM-D-I-VITON) replaces the original TEi43i glass capillary and flow sensor, to maintain constant sample mass flow rate.

Two unheated hydrocarbon kickers remove interference caused by volatile organic compounds which fluoresce at similar UV wavelengths to that of SO₂ fluorescence, and may lead to a false SO₂ amount fraction. The second HC kicker was plumbed in parallel to improve sample flow conductance to the fluorescence cell, to cope with the higher sample mass flow rate, a method first described in Ryerson et al (1998).

Following this initial customisation in 2016, laboratory experimental characterisation for temperature and pressure changes demonstrated a significant increase in instrumental drift, in particular background/baseline signal, which were linked to the instrument manufacturer's pressure and temperature compensation algorithms. These compensation algorithms were therefore disabled, but did not entirely suppress the detector baseline drift.

In order to monitor and correct for baseline drift, frequent (~10 to 15 mins interval) 'zero' calibrations are performed by passing the air sample through an external zero air scrubber cartridge filled with activated charcoal (as used in Teledyne-API model T100 UV fluorescence SO₂ analyser). A three-way electro-solenoid valve (eValve 7, Parker-Hannifin series 9) allows this automated process, which allows the detector to sample a SO₂-free matrix for a set time (45 sec). When performed regularly in-flight, mean amount fraction can be calculated for each in-flight 'zero'. Mean 'zeros' are then linearly interpolated to provide a drift-corrected baseline, which can be subtracted from the raw amount fraction, before being scaled using the detector sensitivity.

A 2 µm particulate filter (Swagelok part no. SS-4FW-2) downstream of the scrubber cartridge protects the TEi43i internal plumbing (e.g. fluorescence cell, optic lenses...) from potential contamination, for instance from activated charcoal dust during zeroing.

Sample inlet and instrument response

From 2012 to 2021, a rear-ward facing ½" OD stainless steel (SS) tube, mounted on a blank BAe-146 aircraft Aluminium window, served as inlet for the TEi43i. The SS tube ID was lined with a ⅜" OD PFA Teflon tube, to accommodate simultaneous atmospheric sampling of ozone, sulphur dioxide and carbon monoxide.

Since 2021, a new pressure-building trace gas inlet has replaced the rear-ward facing inlet. This inlet was initially designed by Richard J. McLaughlin, an instrument design and fabrication specialist at NOAA's Chemical Sciences Division, for NASA's Douglas DC8 (e.g. ATom-2 missions) and NOAA's Lockheed WP-3D Orion aircrafts. The inlet design was first adapted to interface with our aircraft windows by Chris Reed at FAAM in 2019, for use as a fast NO_x measurements inlet.

The new core chemistry McLaughlin inlet is located on starboard windows no. 11 or 12 depending on the cabin configuration (i.e. ~12 to 13 m from the nose of the aircraft). The

picture below illustrates the pylon/shroud inlet mounted on window no. 11 (nose of aircraft to the RHS of picture).

Two of the three inlet internal ports within the pylon are lined with 1/4" OD PFA Teflon tubes, then teed to a single 3/8" OD PFA Teflon tube.

Ambient air is drawn into the aircraft cabin through the 3/8" OD Teflon tube using an all-PTFE Teflon double-headed sample pump (KNF part no. N834.3 FTE). The sample flow (~25 SLPM near surface, degrading to ~ 7 SLPM at 35000') passes through a two-way, normally open, electro-solenoid valve (eValve5, Entegris/Galtek part no. 203-2414-213), used to seal the inlet during pre-flight preparations.

The operation of the KNF sample pump and eValve 5 is automated by the aircraft weight-on-wheels signal; ambient air sampling starts as soon as the aircraft is airborne. This arrangement minimises instrument inlet contamination by airfield polluted air, such as during engines start with aircraft parked on stand, or while taxiing for take-off.

The air sample is transferred to a 3/8" to 1/4" Teflon tee piece (Entegris/Galtek part no part# UT4-6-4N); a short length 1/4" od Teflon tubing connects the tee piece to the TEi43i instrument Nafion dryer.

The excess flow provided by the KNF sample pump is directed to a PFA Teflon buffer volume (PFAVOL) constructed out of three 1 1/2" MNPT 120 mL column segments (Savillex part no. 500-120-02), 3/8" OD tube port closures (Savillex part no. 600-058-19), and female connectors (Savillex part no. 730-0502). The buffer volume is used to dampen oscillating flow effects caused by the KNF sample pump (double diaphragm pressure pulses).

Besides the sequenced in-flight zeroing, a further instrument baseline check can be performed pre- and post-flight using a second external, larger capacity (500 mL), scrubber cartridge (Cole Parmer part no. 01418-50) equipped with in-line PFA filter holder (Entegris part no. 411-4) and 5 μ m PTFE membrane. This scrubber cartridge is half-filled with potassium permanganate coated

alumina spheres (Sofnofil, from Molecular Products Ltd), and activated charcoal, for the removal of NO_x, Ozone and SO₂. During the preparatory phase on the ground, the KNF sample pump is off, cabin air can pass through this larger scrubber cartridge by actuating the three-way electro-solenoid eValve 6 (Entegris/Galtek part no. 203-3414-213), so SO₂-scrubbed cabin air can be sampled by the TEi43i instrument.

During flight, the overflow from the KNF sample pump is constantly monitored by a microbridge mass airflow sensor (MFM, Honeywell model AWM5104VN, 0-20 SLPM), to ensure cabin air is not inadvertently sampled, especially when the inlet pumping performance decreases while approaching our flight ceiling altitude (30000-35000 feet).

The above sampling inlet arrangement enables the TEi43i spectrometer to work within its operating pressure limits, with its inlet pressure effectively following the aircraft cabin pressure.

Based on the current inlet configuration, the instrument lag time (initial signal rise detection) is estimated to be $\sim 4 \pm 1$ sec. The T90 instrumental time response was determined as 18 sec. Please note that no correction for lag time has been applied to our submitted data timestamps.

Calibration and measurement traceability

A 2.5 SLPM mass flow controlled calibration gas mixture of SO₂/Air is used to overflow the instrument inlet by actuating the three-way electro-solenoid eValve 8 (Parker-Hannifin series 9).

Software controlled in-flight calibration sequences were performed using a working standard (BOC HiQ AH-size Spectra-Sealed 5L cylinder, material number 170700-AH-S, cylinder # 190453SG, 374 ppb ± 6%) during the ACRUISE-2 detachment, to provide a single point 'span calibration'. When combined with the drift-corrected baseline, and known working standard concentration, the detector sensitivity can be calculated as $\text{Sensitivity} = (\text{raw_signal} - \text{interpolated_baseline}) / \text{SO}_2\text{_cylinder_conc.}$

The following figure shows a time series of mean in-flight sensitivities for ACRUISE-2 missions C254 to C265. Note that the uncertainty for each sensitivity is largely driven by the uncertainty of the in-flight working standard concentration. The latter was found to be drifting over the course of this study, despite the calibration mixture being held in a specially treated ("Spectra-Seal", BOC proprietary passivation) aluminium cylinder. This was confirmed by regularly analysing the working standard in our laboratories against a dynamically diluted SO₂/air surveillance standard (BOC HiQ AK-size Spectra-Sealed 40L cylinder, material number 154578-AK-S, cylinder # 133668SG, 1030 ppb ± 5%).

The TEi43i sensitivity was also checked on the ground pre-, mid- and post-ACRUISE-2, and post-ACRUISE-3, using dynamically diluted working and surveillance standards. FAAM's dynamic dilution system, consisting of two Alicat Scientific mass flow controllers (see calibration

reports provided in Appendix), generates concentration ranges of 10-74 ppb and 20-200 ppb from the working and surveillance standards respectively.

Mean TEi43i sensitivities were determined during the ACRUISE campaign, based on the calibration reports shown in Appendix, and summarised below.

Calibration	Cylinder #	Sensitivity (gain)	Zero (ppb)
pre-ACRUISE2 6 Aug 2021	133668SG	1.15 ± 0.05	-1.2 ± 2.4 ppb
pre-ACRUISE2 5 Aug 2021	190453SG	1.15 ± 0.05	-1.1 ± 1.5 ppb
mid-ACRUISE2 C259, 5 Oct 2021	190453SG	1.14 ± 0.07	0.2 ± 2.4 ppb
post-ACRUISE2 4 Nov 2021	190453SG	1.21 ± 0.09	0.0 ± 3.5 ppb
post-ACRUISE2 4 Nov 2021	133668SG	1.19 ± 0.03	0.4 ± 2.0 ppb
post-ACRUISE3 12 May 2022	D855647	1.10 ± 0.04	-0.4 ± 0.8 ppb

Measurement uncertainty

For ACRUISE-2 and ACRUISE-3 data, the uncertainty of the detector sensitivity as determined by pre-, mid- and end-of detachment dynamically diluted multi-point calibrations using working and surveillance standards is estimated at ±6% (calibration curve slope), plus an additional ±3% (uncertainty of dynamic dilution system), giving an overall uncertainty of ±9%. The minimum uncertainty is estimated as ±3 ppb based on the interpolated zero uncertainty.

References

T. B. Ryerson, M. P. Buhr, G. J. Frost, P. D. Goldan, J. S. Holloway, G. Hubler, B. T. Jobson, W. C. Kuster, S. A. McKeen, D. D. Parrish, J. M. Roberts, D. T. Sueper, M. Trainer, J. Williams and F. C. Fehsenfeld, Journal of Geophysical Research-Atmospheres, 1998, 103, 22569-22583.

Appendix

Calibration reports

Aug 2021

Oct 2021

Nov 2021

May 2022

SO2 surveillance standards cylinders certificates:

BOC_AH_YorkWACL_SO2_in_N2_cylD855647_1140ppb_cal_certificate.pdf

BOC_AK_Lab_SO2_in_Air_cyl133668SG_1030ppb_cal_certificate.pdf

Sensidyne Gilibrator 3 Dry Cell Calibrator base p/n 610-1701-01-R (s/n 21211001005)

Sensidyne Gilibrator 3 standard flow (50-5000 sccm) cell p/n 610-1703-01-R (s/n 21171011021)

Sensidyne Gilibrator 3 low flow (5-450 sccm) cell p/n 610-1702-01-R (s/n 21191010008)

Calibration Report: TEi-43i TLE SO₂ analyser

Cylinders:		<p>374 ppb ± 6% SO₂/air: material number 170700-AH-S, cylinder # 190453SG</p> <p>1030 ppb ± 5%: material number 154578-AK-S, cylinder # 133668SG</p> <p>(BOC HiQ alpha-volumetric standards)</p> <p>Zero air : BOC BTCA 178 grade, material number 122944-L-C</p>
Measurement Conditions:	<p>Date:</p> <p>Location:</p>	<p>05/08/2021 and 06/08/2021</p> <p>FAAM Laboratory</p>
Instruments:	<p>SO₂ analyser:</p> <p>Dynamic Dilution System:</p>	<p>customised Thermo Fisher Scientific model TEi-43i TLE Pulsed UV Fluorescence Analyser, s/n 1505564557</p> <p>Custom-made system comprising of two Alicat Scientific Mass Flow Controllers, calibrated 30/07/2021 against Sensidyne LP Gilibrator 3 Dry Cell Calibrator</p> <p>MCS-5SLPM-D-I-VITON s/n 60935 gain (1.00 ± 0.003), offset (3.7 ± 3.2)</p> <p>MCS-500SCCM-D-I-VITON s/n 226744 gain (0.98 ± 0.01), offset (-0.8 ± 0.5)</p>
Results cyl # 133668SG	<p>Sensitivity:</p> <p>Zero:</p>	<p>1.15 ± 0.05</p> <p>-1.2 ± 2.4 ppb</p>
Results cyl # 190453SG	<p>Sensitivity:</p> <p>Zero:</p>	<p>1.15 ± 0.05</p> <p>-1.1 ± 1.5 ppb</p>

Measurements

Using the dynamic dilution system, both calibration cylinders and BTCA zero air, blended concentrations ranging 10-74 ppb and 20-200 ppb were produced, respectively. The TEi43i and calibration lines were first conditioned with 20 ppb of SO₂ from cylinder # 133668SG generated with the dynamic dilution system. The concentration of the cylinder (1030 ppb) and the desired concentration were entered into the dynamic dilution system LabVIEW control software, with approximately 5 minutes of flow allowed before selecting the next blended concentration. Zeroes were checked between every two concentrations using BTCA air, by selecting 'Zero' mode on the

dynamic dilution system software. The calibration was repeated using cylinder # 190453SG, the concentration of which had been previously determined by FAAM to be 374 ppb \pm 6% (14/04/2021).

Analysis of calibration data

Calibration data was linearly fitted in Python using orthogonal distance regression, with weighting for summed errors in the x axis (two Alicat MFCs and cylinder uncertainties) and y axis (1σ standard deviation of the TEi43i mean measurement).

Figures 1-2: Sensitivity (m) and SO₂ zero (ppb) (c) of the TEi43i calculated using cylinder # 190453SG (top) and # 133668SG (bottom) SO₂ calibration standards

Calibration Report: TEi-43i TLE SO₂ analyser

Cylinders:		374 ppb ± 6% SO ₂ /air: material number 170700-AH-S, cylinder # 190453SG (BOC HiQ alpha-volumetric standard) Zero air : BOC BTCA 178 grade, material number 178148-AH-C
Measurement Conditions:	Date: Location:	05/10/2021 onboard FAAM aircraft, mission C259 post-flight
Instruments:	SO ₂ analyser: Dynamic Dilution System:	customised Thermo Fisher Scientific model TEi-43i TLE Pulsed UV Fluorescence Analyser, s/n 1505564557 Custom-made system comprising of two Alicat Scientific Mass Flow Controllers, calibrated 30/07/2021 against Sensidyne LP Gilibrator 3 Dry Cell Calibrator MCS-5SLPM-D-I-VITON s/n 60935 gain (1.00 ± 0.003), offset (3.7 ± 3.2) MCS-500SCCM-D-I-VITON s/n 226744 gain (0.98 ± 0.01), offset (-0.8 ± 0.5)
Results	Sensitivity: Zero:	1.14 ± 0.07 0.2 ± 2.4 ppb

Measurements

During the post-flight of mission C259, the TEi43i was calibrated using the cylinder # 190453SG (also used for in-flight calibrations during ACRUISE-2) and the dynamic dilution system and BTCA zero air, over a concentration range of 10-74 ppb. The TEi43i and calibration lines were first conditioned with 20 ppb of SO₂ from cylinder # 190453SG generated with the dynamic dilution system. The concentration of the cylinder (374 ppb) and the desired concentration were entered into the dynamic dilution system LabVIEW control software, with approximately 5 minutes of flow allowed before selecting the next blended concentration. Zeroes were checked between every two concentrations using BTCA air, by selecting 'Zero' mode on the dynamic dilution system software.

Analysis of calibration data

Calibration data was linearly fitted in Python using orthogonal distance regression, with weighting for summed errors in the x axis (two Alicat MFCs and cylinder uncertainties) and y axis (1σ standard deviation of the TEi43i mean measurement).

Figure 1: Sensitivity (m) and SO₂ zero (ppb) (c) of the TEi43i calculated using cylinder # 190453SG SO₂ calibration standard

Calibration Report: TEi-43i TLE SO₂ analyser

Cylinders:		<p>374 ppb ± 6% SO₂/air: material number 170700-AH-S, cylinder # 190453SG</p> <p>1030 ppb ± 5%: material number 154578-AK-S, cylinder # 133668SG</p> <p>(BOC HiQ alpha-volumetric standards)</p> <p>Zero air : BOC BTCA 178 grade, material number 122944-L-C</p>
Measurement Conditions:	<p>Date:</p> <p>Location:</p>	<p>04/11/2021</p> <p>FAAM Laboratory</p>
Instruments:	<p>SO₂ analyser:</p> <p>Dynamic Dilution System:</p>	<p>customised Thermo Fisher Scientific model TEi-43i TLE Pulsed UV Fluorescence Analyser, s/n 1505564557</p> <p>Custom-made system comprising of two Alicat Scientific Mass Flow Controllers, calibrated 30/07/2021 against Sensidyne LP Gilibrator 3 Dry Cell Calibrator</p> <p>MCS-5SLPM-D-I-VITON s/n 60935 gain (1.00 ± 0.003), offset (3.7 ± 3.2)</p> <p>MCS-500SCCM-D-I-VITON s/n 226744 gain (0.98 ± 0.01), offset (-0.8 ± 0.5)</p>
Results cyl # 133668SG	<p>Sensitivity:</p> <p>Zero (ppb):</p>	<p>1.19 ± 0.03</p> <p>0.4 ± 2.0 ppb</p>
Results cyl # 190453SG	<p>Sensitivity:</p> <p>Zero:</p>	<p>1.21 ± 0.09</p> <p>0.0 ± 3.6 ppb</p>

Measurements

Using the dynamic dilution system, both calibration cylinders and BTCA zero air, blended concentrations ranging 25 - 74 ppb and 20 - 150 ppb were produced, respectively. The TEi43i and calibration lines were first conditioned with 20 ppb of SO₂ from the cylinder# 190453SG generated with the dynamic dilution system. The concentration of the cylinder (374 ppb) and the desired concentration were entered into the dynamic dilution system LabVIEW control software, with approximately 5 minutes of flow allowed before selecting the next blended concentration. Zeroes

were checked between every two concentrations using BTCA air, by selecting 'Zero' mode on the dynamic dilution system software.

Undiluted concentrations for each SO₂/Air cylinders were also delivered to the TEi43i using the software controlled in-flight span sequence facility (refer to the SO₂ Instrument Description). This extra step extended the linearisation range to 1030 ppb (surveillance standard cylinder # 133668SG), to check the undiluted concentration of our working standard cylinder# 190453SG (long-term drift check). Before the span sequence facility was used, the BTCA zero air was stopped and the dynamic dilution system disconnected from the TEi43i inlet.

Analysis of calibration data

Calibration data was linearly fitted in Python using orthogonal distance regression, with weighting for summed errors in the x axis (two Alicat MFCs and cylinder uncertainties) and y axis (1 σ standard deviation of the TEi43i mean measurement).

Figures 1-2: Sensitivity (m) and SO₂ zero (ppb) (c) of the TEi43i calculated using cylinder # 190453SG (top) and # 133668SG (bottom) SO₂ calibration standards

Calibration Report: TEi-43i TLE SO₂ analyser

Cylinders:		<i>1140 ppb ± 5% SO₂/nitrogen</i> : material number 156375-AH-S, cyl # D855647 (BOC HiQ alpha-volumetric standard) <i>Zero air</i> : BOC BTCA 178 grade, material number 178148-AH-C
Measurement Conditions:	Date: Location:	12/05/2022 on board FAAM aircraft in Hangar 1
Instruments:	SO ₂ analyser: Dynamic Dilution System:	customised Thermo Fisher Scientific model TEi-43i TLE Pulsed UV Fluorescence Analyser, s/n 1505564557 Custom-made system comprising of two Alicat Scientific Mass Flow Controllers, calibrated 30/07/2021 against Sensidyne LP Gilibrator 3 Dry Cell Calibrator MCS-5SLPM-D-I-VITON s/n 60935 gain (1.00 ± 0.003), offset (3.7 ± 3.2) MCS-500SCCM-D-I-VITON s/n 226744 gain (0.98 ± 0.01), offset (-0.8 ± 0.5)
Results	Sensitivity: Zero:	1.14 ± 0.04 -0.4 ± 0.8 ppb

Measurements

Using the dynamic dilution system, the calibration cylinder and BTCA zero air, blended concentrations ranging 5-100 ppb were produced. The TEi43i and calibration lines were first conditioned with 10 ppb of SO₂ generated with the dynamic dilution system. The concentration of the cylinder (1140 ppb) and the desired concentration were entered into the dynamic dilution system LabVIEW control software, with approximately 5 minutes of flow allowed before selecting the next blended concentration. Zeroes were checked between every two concentrations. The first two zeroes were performed using the activated charcoal zeroing cartridge. For the subsequent two zeroes BTCA air was used, by selecting 'Zero' mode on the dynamic dilution system software.

Analysis of calibration data

Calibration data was linearly fitted in Python using orthogonal distance regression, with weighting for summed errors in the x axis (two Alicat MFCs and cylinder uncertainties) and y axis (1σ standard deviation of the TEi43i mean measurement).

Figure 1: Sensitivity (m) and SO₂ zero (c) of the TEi43i using calibration cylinde # D855647

FAAM SO2/air surveillance standard cylinder # 133668SG

Certificate

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COMPONENT	NOMINAL COMPOSITION	CERTIFIED VALUE
SULPHUR DIOXIDE SYNTHETIC AIR		1 PPM = 1.03 PPM BAL

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CERTIFICATE NO.: 21/001085
 CERTIFICATE DATE: 13 JAN 2021 USE BY: 12 JAN 2026
 APPROVED SIGNATORY Sofiane Hadjiliah

PROD ORDER 2789073 BARCODE NUMBER 21901310019969 CYLINDER NO. 133668SG MATERIAL 154578-AK-S PAGE 1 of 2

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CYLINDER DETAILS :
 Cylinder Size: AK 40.00 Litres Valve outlet: BS14
 Nominal cylinder contents: 200.0 Bar(t) at 15°C

Certified values have an uncertainty of <=5%, and have been determined using standards traceable to internationally recognised reference materials, or relevant ISO standards.

STABILITY ASSURED until the use by date.
 Composition is expressed on a molar basis unless otherwise specified.
 Do not use below 5% of actual contents.
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University of York, Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry Laboratories, SO₂/N₂ surveillance standard

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COMPONENT	NOMINAL COMPOSITION	CERTIFIED VALUE
SULPHUR DIOXIDE		1 PPM = 1.14 PPM
NITROGEN	BAL	

CERTIFICATE NO.: 21/013857
CERTIFICATE DATE: 21 MAY 2021 **USE BY:** 20 MAY 2026
APPROVED SIGNATORY Sofiane Hadjiliah

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PROD ORDER	BARCODE NUMBER	CYLINDER NO.	MATERIAL	PAGE
2800795	21901520043358	D855647	156375-AH-S	1 of 2

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To reorder, please quote 156375 AH SPECTRA-SEAL CERTIFIED

CYLINDER DETAILS:
Cylinder Size: AH - 5.00 Litres Valve outlet: BS14
Nominal cylinder contents: 200.0 Bar(g) at 15°C

Certified values have an uncertainty of $\pm 5\%$, and have been determined using standards traceable to internationally recognised reference materials, or relevant ISO standards.

STABILITY ASSURED until the use by date.

Composition is expressed on a molar basis unless otherwise specified.
Do not use below 5% of actual contents.
Store and use between -5° & 50°C unless otherwise specified.

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PROD ORDER	BARCODE NUMBER	CYLINDER NO.	MATERIAL	PAGE
2800795	21901520043358	D855647	156375-AH-S	2 of 2

Sensidyne LP Gilibrator 3 certificates

Sensidyne Certificate of Performance Gilibrator 3 Calibrator Base

This document certifies that the product listed below performs in accordance with factory specifications. Sensidyne's test equipment is traceable to National Institute of Standards (NIST).

Sensidyne, LP is an ISO 9001:2015 registered company.

Gilian Gilibrator 3 Calibrator Base: P/N 610-1701-01-R
Date: May 25, 2021
Serial Number: 21211001005 Firmware Version: V2.5.0
Temperature: 22.1 °C Pressure: 1024.2 hPa

Test Parameter	Pass
Serial Number Checked	✓
Firmware Version V2.5.0 Checked	✓
Temperature Checked	✓
Temperature Units of Measure Checked	✓
Pressure Differential Checked	✓
Barometric Pressure Checked	✓
Calibration Date Checked	✓
Valve Leak Checked	✓
Auto Brightness Checked	✓
Battery Health Checked	✓
Filter Health Checked	✓
Direction Valve Angle Calibrated	✓
Backpressure Compensation Valve Calibrated	✓
Clock Set	✓
Touch Screen Calibrated	✓
Languages Checked	✓
Battery Drained for Shipping	✓

Technician Stamp: GG

ISO/IEC 17025 Calibration Certificate

Certificate Number: 21171011021-S 05-25-2021

Customer Information

Sensidyne LP
1000 112th Circle North, Suite 100
St. Petersburg, FL 33716

Calibration Date: May 25, 2021

Procedure: WI0031

Flow Cell Information

Description	Serial Number	Firmware Version
Gilibrator 3 Standard Flow Dry Cell	21171011021	V2.4 R1951

Laboratory Environmental Conditions

Temperature: 21.8 °C Pressure: 1024.4 hPa Relative Humidity: 54.1 %

Measurement Data *Performed Using Vacuum Source

Nominal Value (Mean Value of 5 samples)	Measured Value (Mean Value of 5 samples)	Specification	Relative Difference (Mean Value of 5 samples)	Percent Difference (%) (Mean Value of 5 samples)
52.46	52.57	±1%	0.11	0.21
1262.8	1267.05	±1%	4.25	0.34
2535.2	2546.67	±1%	11.47	0.45
3819.6	3843.04	±1%	23.44	0.61
4993	5023.97	±1%	30.97	0.62

The As Found Data was collected with the referenced Gilibrator 3 base. This cell data may not be relied upon if combined with a different Gilibrator 3 base.

Calibration Standards

Serial Number	Description	Cal Due Date
MCS-102B	Standard Wet Cell (Master)	August 31, 2021
MCL-103B	Low Wet Cell (Master)	August 31, 2021
A.024402	Environmental Meter	September 22, 2021

Sensidyne certifies that the instrument specified above meets the manufacturer's specification and was calibrated using the standards and instruments listed above that are traceable to the International System of Units (SI) through the National Institute of Standards and Testing (NIST). Our calibration systems and records are in compliance to ISO/IEC 17025:2017. Unless requested by the customer, the measurement uncertainty has not been included in determining compliance to specifications. The reported measurement uncertainty of 0.82% is stated as the combined standard uncertainty, multiplied by a coverage factor K=2. The measured value and the associated expanded uncertainty is expressed at 95% confidence level. The measurement values range, including the estimated uncertainty of measurement, shall fall within the specification limit.

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ISO/IEC 17025 Calibration Certificate

Certificate Number: 21191010008-L 05-12-2021

Customer Information

Sensidyne LP
1000 112th Circle North, Suite 100
St. Petersburg, FL 33716

Calibration Date: May 12, 2021
Procedure: WI0032

Flow Cell Information

Description	Serial Number	Firmware Version
Gilibrator 3 Low Flow Dry Cell	21191010008	V2.4 R1951

Laboratory Environmental Conditions

Temperature: 22.6 °C Pressure: 1019.0 hPa Relative Humidity: 58.3 %

Measurement Data *Performed Using Vacuum Source

Nominal Value (Mean Value of 5 samples)	Measured Value (Mean Value of 5 samples)	Specification	Relative Difference (Mean Value of 5 samples)	Percent Difference (%) (Mean Value of 5 samples)
7.21	7.19	±1%	-0.02	-0.28
115.8	115.87	±1%	0.07	0.06
225.56	225.93	±1%	0.37	0.16
343.2	343.07	±1%	-0.13	-0.04
453.86	453.36	±1%	-0.5	-0.11

The As Found Data was collected with the referenced Gilibrator 3 base. This cell data may not be relied upon if combined with a different Gilibrator 3 base.

Calibration Standards

Serial Number	Description	Cal Due Date
MCS-102B	Standard Wet Cell (Master)	August 31, 2021
MCL-103B	Low Wet Cell (Master)	August 31, 2021
A.024402	Environmental Meter	September 22, 2021

Sensidyne certifies that the instrument specified above meets the manufacturer's specification and was calibrated using the standards and instruments listed above that are traceable to the International System of Units (SI) through the National Institute of Standards and Testing (NIST). Our calibration systems and records are in compliance to ISO/IEC 17025:2017. Unless requested by the customer, the measurement uncertainty has not been included in determining compliance to specifications. The reported measurement uncertainty of 0.82% is stated as the combined standard uncertainty, multiplied by a coverage factor K=2. The measured value and the associated expanded uncertainty is expressed at 95% confidence level. The measurement values range, including the estimated uncertainty of measurement, shall fall within the specification limit.

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Calibrated By

Approved By

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